

Effect of Microstructural Damage on the Thermomechanical Properties of Composite Electrodes in Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cells

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CONTENTS

- Background
- Methods
- Results and discussion
- Conclusion

Proton exchange membrane fuel cells (PEMFC)

Chemical energy \rightarrow Electrical energy

Transportation & Stationary power plants

Damage Failure Affects PEMFC Durability

- Electrode component: most likely to suffer damage

Thermomechanical Degradation

➤ Damage due to mechanical and thermal actions

Start-up and shutdown condition

Hydrothermal loading cycles

Multiscale Simulation

- Microstructural changes and macroscopic properties

Preparation

Schematic

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Research Methods and Framework

Representative Volume Element (RVE)

Characteristic	Matrix	Pt/C	Pore
Size (nm)	100	20-50	20-100
Volume fraction	30-55	15-40	30-40

➤ Interface interaction

- Friction

$$\tau = \mu P + P_0$$

- Delamination

$$T = K\delta(1 - D_m)$$

➤ Interface delamination model: mixed cohesive zone model

$$T = K\delta(1 - D)$$

$$D = \begin{cases} 0 & , \delta \leq \delta^* \\ \left(\frac{\delta - \delta^*}{\delta}\right) \left(\frac{\delta^c}{\delta^c - \delta^*}\right) & , \delta^* < \delta < \delta^c \\ 1 & , \delta > \delta^c \end{cases}$$

Mechanical parameters

Diversity and sizes

➤ Interface adhesive force (AFM Experiment)

Measurement

- ▣ Maximum force: 3.74~8.42 nN
- ▣ Adhesive strength: 47.4~106.7 MPa

Results (11 samples)

➤ Interface adhesive force (MD simulation)

Molecular model

Force-displacement curve

➤ Interfacial thermal conductivity

$$Q = \frac{\kappa A t \Delta T}{x}$$

$$J = -\kappa \frac{dT}{dx}$$

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➤ Interface type & mechanical parameters

Model	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	T_t^{max} (MPa)	T_s^{max} (MPa)	δ_t^* (nm)	δ_s^* (nm)	δ_t^c (nm)	δ_s^c (nm)
Type I	11.12	13.58	5.44	0.044	2.356	0.925	5.826
Type II	21.47	24.73	6.81	0.046	3.544	0.927	5.657
Type III	38.73	43.57	16.87	0.046	3.689	0.940	6.029

➤ Interfacial thermal conductivity

➤ Electrode's mechanical property

Interfacial strength \propto Elastic modulus

Interface	E_b (kcal/mol)	E_0 /MPa	σ_y /MPa	ϵ_y /%	ν
Type I	11.12	138.38	1.40	1.018	0.291
Type II	21.47	139.02	1.41	1.014	0.290
Type III	38.73	141.16	1.44	1.021	0.284
Type IV	∞	153.30	1.53	0.934	0.262

Delamination evolution \rightleftharpoons Sudden stop in stress

➤ Electrode's mechanical properties

Model	E_0/MPa	σ_y/MPa	$\epsilon_y/\%$	ν
RVE I	138.38	1.40	1.02	0.291
RVE II	123.77	1.25	1.01	0.303
RVE III	134.27	1.38	1.03	0.239

Three RVE models with Type I-Interface

➤ Electrode's thermal conductivity

85 °C → 25 °C

Interface	ITC ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1}$)	Strain	Porosity (%)	$k_c (W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot K^{-1})$
Type IV	0	0	28	0.1121
Type II	MD results	0	28	0.0735
Type II	MD results	0.1	30	0.0632
Type I	MD results	0.085	31	0.0541

MD results

Temperature (°C)	ITC ($W \cdot m^{-1} \cdot k^{-1}$)
25	0.0054
45	0.0056
65	0.0057
80	0.0064

➤ Electrode's thermal conductivity

- Effective medium theory

$$\sum_{i=1}^s f_i \frac{k_c - k_i}{k_i + (z/2 - 1)k_c} = 0$$

- f_i volume fraction (i th phase)
- k_i thermal conductivity (i th phase)
- k_c thermal conductivity (composite)

Comparison

Interface	Porosity (%)	$k_c(\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1})$ (Present)	$k_c(\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1})$ (EMT)
Type II	28	0.0735	0.093
Type II	30	0.0632	0.085
Type I	31	0.0541	0.081

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Thermomechanical Properties of Damaged Electrode

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Thank You For Your Attention!